

THE INFLUENCE OF SOLIDIFICATION ON THE INTERFACE OF CF/Al-4.5Cu COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, CF/Al-4.5Cu composites was fabricated by using of squeeze cast method, and then the microstructures in the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites were observed and analysed by means of SEM and TEM. As results, when the solidification cooling rate decreased, crystallize quantity of θ -CuAl₂ phase in the interface region decreased and microsegregation of Cu element around carbon fiber surface also decreased, but the size of θ -CuAl₂ phase increased. As the solidification cooling rate increased, crystallize quantity of reaction product Al₄C₃ in the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites was increased, but the size of Al₄C₃ phase decreased.

KEYWORDS: CF/Al-4.5Cu composites, interface, solidification, cooling rate

INTRODUCTION

Since carbon fiber (CF) reinforced metal matrix composites have a high specific strength, high specific modules and excellent high temperature characteristics, so a lot of works were dealt with it [1]. But the strength of CF/Al composites fabricated by liquid infiltration method almost can not reach the calculation value by theory (ROM value), it is suggested that the interfacial reactions of CF/Al composites have a serious effect on the strength of the composites [2].

The interface is an important component of CF/Al composites, the interface of metal matrix composites is related to a lot of factors, such as the microstructure of the interface, adhesion and chemical reaction between reinforcement and matrix, as well as diffusion of alloy elements between two phases, therefore the interface is a very complicated problem. Previously there are not quite understand for forming process on the microstructure of interface and influence of the interface on mechanical properties of composites, but recently a lot of research works are engaged on the interface [3,4], such as: interface chemical reaction, the interface microstructure, the effect of the interface on mechanical properties of composites, the influence of thermal treatment on the interface reaction and microstructure, the relation of interface microstructure with failure and damage of composites, et al. But, due to the interface microstructure and its forming process are very complicated, they are effected by the manufacturing of technologies, processing parameters, applied condition, and environment, so that there are only few works relate to interface theory.

In this paper, CF/Al-4.5Cu composites will be selected as investigation object, to study the relationship of reaction products in the interface with solidification process and recognize sufficiently on the interface of CF/Al composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Composites Preparation

CF/Al-4.5Cu composites was fabricated by squeeze cast method, the schematic diagram of squeeze cast apparatus was shown in Fig.1. The processing parameters were divided into two groups:

(A) pouring temperature of Al-4.5Cu alloy was 800°C, the preheating temperature of carbon fibers (CF) preforms T_f was 500°C, the preheating temperature of the mould was 300°C;

(B) pouring temperature of Al-4.5Cu alloy was 820°C, the preheating temperature of carbon fibers (CF) preforms T_f was 600°C and the preheating temperature of the mould was 400°C.

Two groups of samples were produced by squeeze casting process under the pressure of 100 MPa, the loading time of constant pressure was 3 minutes, and the volume fraction of fibers V_f in composites are about 45%.

Fig.1: Schematic diagram of a apparatus for squeeze cast MMCs.

Interface Microstructure Analyses

Specimens were first cut into pieces by the linear cutting machine, with a thickness of 0.5 mm, and mechanically polished to a thickness about 100 μ m, then mechanically thinned on a Gatan 656/3 polished machine and reduce the thickness to approximately 15 μ m, final thinning was carried out by using of argonion plasma bombardment by Gatan model 600-TMP machine. All thinned specimens were stored in a freezer to prevent possible natural aging when not in use. The interface microstructure was observed in the TEM 420 with EDAX at 300 KV of operating voltage.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Relationship of CuAl_2 Phase Precipitated in the Interface with Solidification Process

Fig.2 shows the interface microstructures of different samples of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites fabricated by squeeze cast. By comparing the interface microstructure in cross-section of sample A with B, it is obviously that eutectic $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase formed on the surface of carbon fiber and with increase of preheating temperature of CF, crystallize quantity of $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase decrease and the shape of $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase is changed from block-like to particle-like or worm-like. The reason is that, according to the phase diagram of Al-4.5Cu alloy [5], an eutectic reaction will occur under nonequilibrium solidification condition, quantity of precipitated $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase depends mainly on the degree of the solidus moved leftward and according to the lever rule and the quantity of precipitated $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase increased with the increase of degree of the solidus moved leftward. From A to B, the solidification cooling rate decreased with increase of preheating temperature of reforms, and in the meantime, the degree of solidus moved leftward decreased, which can be accounted by the decrease of the quantity of $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase.

Fig.2: Distribution of CuAl_2 phase in the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites

Comparing the interface microstructures of specimen A with B, the size of eutectic $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase of B is larger than that of A, it is due to the cooling rate between them was different, in which the preheating temperature of B was higher than that of A, so that cooling rate of B is lower than A. According to solidification theory, if the cooling rate is lower, solidification process needs long time in the local area and the precipitated phase is bigger at the same time. For this reason, the eutectic phase of specimen B is bigger than that of A.

The Relationship of Al_4C_3 Phase Precipitated with Solidification Process

The interface microstructures are further examined by a transmission electron microscopy (TEM), it is shown that the interface microstructures has evidently effected by manufacture technology parameters. During processing of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites, the important technology parameter is a solidification cooling rate, because at higher temperature, the time of CF contacting with liquid or solid aluminum alloy will greatly influence on the forming kinetics of the carbon-aluminum reaction compound [6].

Fig.3 shows the distribution of Al_4C_3 in the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites fabricated by squeeze cast under the condition of different technology parameters such as A and B. These results suggest that the quantity of precipitated Al_4C_3 phase in A specimen is obviously more than that in B, but the dimension of precipitated Al_4C_3 phase in A is smaller than that in B.

Fig.3 Distribution of Al_4C_3 phase in the interface of CF/Al-4.5 Cu composites

During processing of metal matrix composites, the solidification cooling rate does influence on shape, size and distribution of precipitated phases. In the case of squeezing cast CF/Al-4.5Cu composites, the factors of the influence on solidification cooling rate are pouring temperature of liquid metal, preheating temperature of preform and mould temperature, et al. So that, the cooling rate of specimen A is lower than B.

Fig.4 shows the SAD pattern of the Al_4C_3 phase and $CuAl_2$ phase in B specimen, it identifies that Al_4C_3 and $CuAl_2$ phase precipitated in the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites.

Fig. 4 The SAD pattern of $CuAl_2$ and Al_4C_3 phase in the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites

Previously some works [7,8] have showed that Cu element accumulate easily in the interface of composites, it is because that probably reducing the interface energy according to Gibbs' interface absorption theory. For specimen A and B, Fig.5 shows Cu element segregation surrounding CF and the extent of Cu element segregation in specimen A is larger than B.

According to forming mechanism of the segregation suggested by literature [9] that before forming Al_4C_3 , Cu atoms have accumulated on the surface of CF first and during the growth of Al_4C_3 by interface reaction, Cu atoms are necessary as an initiator. When the segregation extent of Cu element is more large, the rendered Al atoms are turn to small. So since the segregation extent of Cu element in specimen A is larger than B, under the same condition of the interface reaction, the amount of Al atoms rendered by specimen A is lower than B.

(a) Specimen A

(b) Specimen B

Fig.5: Distribution of Cu element around carbon fiber surface.

In the meanwhile, with the decreasing of solidification cooling rate, the touching time between carbon fiber and liquid Al will increase, it means the interface reaction time is also prolonged by comparing A with B. Due to the touching time and temperature between carbon fiber and liquid Al alloy will greatly effect on the forming kinetics of carbon-aluminum reaction compound, so that with increase of the touching time and temperature, the forming condition for carbon-aluminum reaction compound is easier, therefore, it would lead that the size of precipitated Al_4C_3 in B case is larger than that in A, and with the increase of Cu element segregation, the diffusion hinder effect for Al atoms increased, i.e. the diffusion of Al atom becomes difficult and restricts the growth of Al_4C_3 .

Besides, when the CuAl_2 forming, it will restrict the growth of Al_4C_3 and trend to precipitate $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase intensively, so that the dimension of Al_4C_3 phase in case A is smaller than B. Normally, the quantity of precipitated Al_4C_3 phase in specimen B should be large than A, but actually it is inverse since the nucleation rate of Al_4C_3 phase in specimen A is higher than B.

CONCLUSIONS

1. In the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composite fabricated by squeeze cast, with decrease of solidification cooling rate, the extent of Cu element segregation on the surface is decreased and the quantity of precipitated $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase is also decreased, but the size of $\theta\text{-CuAl}_2$ phase is increased.

2. TEM analysis showed that in the interface of CF/Al-4.5Cu composites fabricated by squeeze cast, the quantity of precipitated Al_4C_3 is increased with increase of solidification cooling rate, but the size of Al_4C_3 phase is decreased.

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